

Smart Learning Applications with the combination of the Open Research Knowledge Graph and Teaching Knowledge Graphs

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Abstract. Domain Knowledge Graphs (KGs) are increasingly adopted in education to support research and teaching in higher institutions. With the rise of Generative AI and its growing integration into these domains, KGs play a pivotal role in ensuring the quality and verifiability of educational resources, including content accuracy and source reliability. This vision paper explores the synergy between two semantic web initiatives, the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) and the Teaching Knowledge Graph for Knowledge Graph education, to advance Knowledge Graph-driven education. We outline the problem statement, review the state-of-the-art, and propose three real-world scenarios where integrating knowledge from these KGs can enhance smart learning applications and research support. Our work highlights the potential of combined KGs to improve e-learning while addressing challenges in content trustworthiness and AI-augmented education.

Keywords: Scholarly data · Technology-enhanced Learning · KGs in Education.

Combining scholarly and educational data

Semantic Web technologies have gained momentum in applications in scholarly and educational data [15, 1]. While vast amounts of research are published daily across venues and journals, integrating scholarly data into formal education remains limited, manual, and ad hoc. In parallel, adaptive learning technologies have made significant advances in personalizing content delivery and understanding the learner state, however, they often rely on static knowledge bases that are disconnected from the dynamic world of academic research [2]. Currently, existing systems fall short in tightly coupling state-of-the-art scientific knowledge with educational content in a scalable, machine-interpretable, and pedagogically meaningful way [7]. This disconnect results in curricula that are disconnected from scientific discovery, educators who lack tools to contextualize and integrate cutting-edge research into their teaching material, and learners who miss out on opportunities to engage with evidence-based knowledge from the latest research advancements. To address this challenge, we propose bridging forces with

the Open Research Knowledge Graph and the Teaching Knowledge Graph with Generative Artificial Intelligent (GenAI), as visualized in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Bridging Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) and Teaching Knowledge Graphs with higher education resources can enable smart learning applications, such as offering content in multi-modal formats, learning analytics, trend identification and summary of the latest advancements in the scientific domain of choice.

ORKG: The scholarly data

The Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) [3] is an advanced digital infrastructure designed to semantically represent, organize, and interlink scholarly knowledge. Unlike traditional academic databases that rely primarily on unstructured text, the ORKG facilitates machine-actionable, structured scholarly communication. It allows researchers to collaboratively describe research contributions in a structured manner using KGs, making it easier to compare, integrate, and analyze scientific information across disciplines. Key features include: Semantic representation of research contributions (methods, results, problems, etc.); Interoperability and linking with external data sources (like Wikidata, ORCID, Geonames); Collaborative curation by the research community; Enabling automated reasoning, literature comparisons, and knowledge-based discovery. The ORKG ultimately aims to enhance the transparency, accessibility, and reusability of scientific knowledge, contributing to open science and the acceleration of research.

Teaching KG: The educational data

The Teaching Knowledge Graph (TKG) for Knowledge Graphs education is a new initiative aimed to support the Semantic Web community in interlinking

resources and educators in KG-related topics [9, 7]. The TKG uses a higher ontology to interlink three distinct layers: (1) topics and skills, (2) courses and lectures, with (3) educational material. The topics and skills are described by the experts of the community offering insights to the complexity and work load required for each lecture corresponding to specific topics. The courses are voluntarily provided by the community in order to interconnect the curricula in similar resources and lectures. Finally, theoretical and practical educational material are added to assist discovery of relevant educational resources for topics and courses. Additionally, TKG utilizes semantic rules and adds a pedagogical framework that proposes necessary elements present in course description, such as the license of the online-available material.

Smart Learning Applications: Potential and Challenges

KGs can be used to achieve smart learning applications [11, 12], and the combination of the ORKG and the TKG with GenAI presents a transformative opportunity to actualize adaptive, research-grounded smart learning environments, as we describe three use cases in Table 1. The ORKG structure offers a continuously updated evidence base with semantic representation of scholarly literature and knowledge reviews, and data sets. In parallel, TKG captures educational resources such as curricula, skills, and educational material provided by the experts in the field. Their integration establishes a foundation for educational AI-powered systems that dynamically align instructional content with the frontier of scientific discovery while tailoring learning experiences to individual needs offering multi-modality, multi-linguality, alternative means of learning content presentation and summary [4], and accessibility [8] tailored to the user needs and preferences.

Table 1. Presentation of three smart learning scenarios and the elements used by ORKG and Teaching KG for each.

Scenario	ORKG	Teaching KG	Smart Learning
I want 10 slides on the new research topic X	Finds similar research papers and literature reviews	Maps subtopics, skills, curricula (learning order), and educational material	Research highlights, Learning objectives, Concept progression flow
Give me an engaging learning content on topic X	Links to datasets and research papers from topic X	Selects theoretical and practical educational material on the given topic	Multi-modal adaptive content generation
Help me understand this part in the Jupiter notebook	Finds research papers on the topic	Gets topics and skills, and retrieves educational material in connected topics	Automatic topic detection and code content breakdown based on prerequisites

At the foundation of this vision lies the intelligent generation and adaptation of educational content, enabled by three interlocking technological pillars: knowledge fusion, learning assistants, and explainable quality-driven content generation. We aim to develop an iterative step-by-step learning methodology similar to successful gamified-learning companies for language learning, by leverage GenAI neural models for the generation of interactive learning material. This

can be achieved via a neuro-symbolic framework for integrating ORKG’s formalized research assertions with TKG’s pedagogical models to generate context-sensitive, personalized learning resources. For instance, when introducing the topic of "reinforcement learning", the system could automatically embed the latest ORKG-curated benchmarks (e.g., NeurIPS datasets) into an interactive Jupyter notebook, adjusting the complexity to suit the learner’s background and prior exposure.

Following, AI-driven neuro-symbolic tutors [13] that utilize the unified ORKG-TKG graph can deliver real-time, research-informed support. These assistants can contextualize concepts, recommend personalized learning trajectories, and transform SPARQL-retrieved scholarly content into micro-lessons, adaptive quizzes, or data-driven visualizations. Moreover, they can be combined with research lab KG data to identify relevant researchers for collaboration and reveal potential emerging trends within institutions [5]. Furthermore, a closed feedback loop incorporating learner interactions with the platforms and the ORKG ASK [14] can inform updates to the learner’s graph in the TKG [6]. Consequently, these updates can trigger the retrieval and integration of alternative pedagogical materials and frameworks, fostering a system that continuously refines itself in response to empirical learner data.

Challenges Despite the potential opportunities there are persistent challenges, such as semantic interoperability, cross-domain ontology alignment, and the automatization of the pipeline. Emerging advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) could assist in overcoming these barriers, despite the potential risks in hallucinations. Also, educational and research content is governed by varied copyrights, licenses (e.g., CC-BY), and access agreements, which hinders the digital integration as converting pay-walled or restricted research into teaching materials risks IP violations without proper licensing and attribution. Generative AI and LLMs further complicate derivative works and fair use, which without clear standards, and rights management uncertainties could hinder the harmonious integration of ORKG and TKG.

Furthermore, an open research problem remains the meaningful understanding user inquiries and detection of the relevant content and underlying user needs. Another important challenge in personalization is the selection and presentation of content at an appropriate level of granularity. Additionally, properly evaluating the integration of ORKG-TKG into a neuro-symbolic hybrid system may require the development of new benchmarks and metrics [10].

Summary This vision re-imagines the role of educational technologies between higher education and scholarly data not as a passive consumer of knowledge, but as a co-evolving agent within the broader knowledge ecosystem, which closes the loop between discovery, dissemination, and learning.

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